

SHORT-TERM RESULTS OF CORE DECOMPRESSION OF POST-COVID FEMORAL HEAD ASEPTIC NECROSIS

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The coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (COVID-19) pandemic has stimulated an unprecedented response by the global scientific community to better understand the disease. However, many questions about SARS-CoV-2 remain unanswered. Various hypotheses have been formulated in regard to its pathogenetic mechanisms. One of them single nucleotide polymorphisms in various genes encode for proinflammatory proteins, such as IL-1b, IL-6 and IL-8, which may affect biological activity and contribute to hypercoagulability in COVID-19 patients, thereby increasing the risk of thrombosis of femoral head vessels and its aseptic necrosis or avascular necrosis (AVN).

Aim To evaluate the short-term results of surgical treatment of Aseptic Necrosis at early stages according to VAS (visual analogue scale).

Materials and methods. This retrospective study was conducted from September 2020 till June 2022 in Tashkent, Akfa Medline Clinic. We have chosen VAS for assessment of the clinical improvement after core decompression (CD). This study was conducted among 22 AVN patients in early stage of disease, who suffered from coronavirus infection and taken steroids as treatment. Youngest patient was 23 and oldest 72 years old, average – 44 with both sex distributions. Half of them CD was performed bilateral, half of them unilateral decompression. VAS score measured day before surgery and 2nd post-operation day.

Results. There were 34 joints was involved to the study. 32% patients were diagnosed on MRI Ficat 1 stage, 45% Ficat 2nd stage and 23% - Ficat 3rd stage. The mean VAS score day before surgery was 6.5, and post-operative day was average 2.3 ($p < 0.005$). Later in 1 patient 67 years old was complication, as femoral head collapse.

Conclusion. Core decompression is an effective and safe method of treating post-covid AVN in early stages, it gives good clinical improvement due to pain relief. High-quality randomized controlled trials and prospective studies will be necessary to further clarify the effectiveness of CD.

Adam Sulewski, Dominik Sieron, Karol Szyluk, Mikołaj Da Browski, Lukasz Kubaszewski, Dawid Lukoszek and Andreas Christe, Avascular Necrosis Bone

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